

FAILURE ASPECTS OF FIBER METAL LAMINATES AFTER LOW VELOCITY AND LOW ENERGY IMPACT

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1 Introduction

Fiber Metal Laminates (FML) are new kind of hybrid composite materials [1]. The major advantages of FMLs are their superior fatigue resistance, high strength properties, impact and corrosion resistance [1,2]. Low-velocity Impact resistance is a one of the important issue for composite structures, particularly in aerospace. According to Sohn et al. [4] impact damage is occurring during pre-flight and taxiing operations, runway debris, hail, or bird strikes, maintenance damage (e.g., dropped tools), collision between service cars or cargo and the structure, ice from propellers striking the fuselage, engine debris and tire shrapnel from tread separation and tire rupture. In recent years, several studies had been conducted to investigate failure mechanisms after impact. Impact damage of GLARE, and other aluminum-based FMLs have been examined by Vlot et al. [5] and other researchers [6-9]. Lawcock et al. [9] characterized the effect of fiber/matrix adhesion on the impact properties of carbon fiber-reinforced metal laminates. The purpose of the study was identification of failure differences in carbon composite laminates after low velocity impact.

2 Materials and methodology

The subject of examination were carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) and carbon fiber metal laminates composed of thin aluminum layers with carbon reinforced polymer (Al/CFRP). The 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheets with 0.5 mm thickness were used. The composite layers in both kind of materials were consists of unidirectional prepregs (Hexcel, USA) based on AS7J high-strength carbon fibers with epoxy matrix resin (thickness of 0.131 mm). The nominal fiber content was about 60 vol.%. Before laminating, the surface

of aluminum alloy sheets were anodized in chromic acid electrolyte and next, adhesive primer to improve bonding with fiber reinforced polymers was applied. The final thickness of both type composites was about 1.5 mm. Al/CFRP Laminates were prepared as 2/1 in the Al/CFRP(0/90)₂/Al sequence. CFRP composites were prepared in configurations (0/90)₆. All subject materials has been produced at the Department of Materials Engineering in Lublin University of Technology (Poland) by autoclave method (Scholz Maschinenbau, Germany).

Samples were subjected to low velocity impact in room temperature by using a drop-weight impact tester (INSTRON 9340). It was used a hemispherical impactor tip with a diameter of 0.5 and 1.5". All tests were conducted based on ASTM D7136 standard different energies – 2.5, and 5J. After impact samples were tested by using NDT and microscopic methods to note failure of laminates.

3 Results and discussion

Typical examples of samples damage after low velocity impact shows Figure 1 (ultrasonic view).

Fig. 1. Impact damage of CFRP (0/90)₆ under 2.5 J low-velocity impact (phased array view).

It can be seen that impact phenomena causes internal failure in both kind of composites [4,7]. Composites can contain barely visible impact damage (BVID). The damage area of CFRP it is quite similar to FML,

but in FML it include plastic deformation also. Moreover the ultrasonic view shows that the damage has delaminations character because the shape of failure depends on the layer configuration [7] and it can be noted differences in attenuation of ultrasonic waves – delaminations between different layers. FML damage is characterized by plastic deformation where is difficult to say about failure nature. Failure after impact is presented on Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Cross section of CFRP (a) and Al/CFRP (b) after 5J impact.

Presented fracture of composites indicates the complex character of material failure after low velocity impact especially for classic composite laminates (CFRP). Matrix damage is the first type of failure. The second is debonding between fibre or matrix also and for FMLs between metal and composite. It can be noted delaminations with cohesive and adhesive nature. The same observations are in another studies [7,9]. Numerous transverse cracks between layers arranged in a cone (top of the impact location - impacted side) were observed especially for CFRP composite (Fig. 2a). They are connecting numerous delaminations between the layers. For Al/CFRP this type of crack were noted, but much less. Transverse cracks are located in circumference of impact point [4]. They are through all thickness of polymer inside FML. Actually, transverse cracks are the only mechanism for the destruction of FMLs after impact to 5J impact energy. For them higher energies cause delaminations, especially in the interface of the metal and composite [7-9].

4 Conclusions

- Failure of classic composite materials is complex. The most common are delaminations in cohesive interface and connecting them by transverse cracks.
- CFRP laminates are degraded in a determined manner. Cone transverse cracks, radiating from the point of impact, many delaminations connected together were observed.
- Fiber Metal Laminates characterized by much less transverse cracking without delaminations in favor of metal-composite interface degradation.
- Fiber Metal Laminates have better low velocity impact resistance taking into account the caused failure.

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